

FREQUENCY CONJUGATE ELEMENTS IN M GROUP

Dr. Moloy Dutta

Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, T.M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, I have tried to define Frequency conjugate elements in the context of Multigroup or M group. Also, I have provided introduction, historical background, required definitions and results related to this topic that need to be highlighted. These definitions and results will encourage new researchers in the future.

Introduction:

Set theory was expanded by German mathematician G. Cantor in 19th century. In this type of set which is called an ordinary set, an element occurs only once. Currently another type of set-concept gaining popularity that is called Multiset or *Mset* in short. Basic difference between that two concepts is, ordinary set does not allow repetition while multiset allow repetition. Also, in ordinary set theory there exist two connections between two elements, either equal or different, while in *Mset* theory number of possible connections between two elements is three, maybe they are different, maybe they are same but separate, or maybe they are identically coincided. For instance, in single molecule of nitric acid contains one hydrogen, and one nitrogen and three oxygen atoms. We may also face repetition in the case of factorization a number, storing duplicates elements in sorted manner in C++, digitizing DNA sequence etc. These examples shows that how important this topic is to us and the concept of repetition is more important when objects are present physically.

Literature Review:

After D.E. Knuth and N.G. deBruijn introduced the term 'multiset' to the world of mathematics in 1971, R. R. Yager and J.L. Peterson's contributions to this field were significant. Wayne D Blizard studied several axioms on this topic in 1989. The idea of multiset space was given by S. P. Jena et al. in 2001. D. Sing and J. N. Sing contributed some proofs of combinational properties of Multiset in the year 2003. K.P. Girish & S.J. John brought multisets to the world of mathematics in a completely new way and they also showed us how to define relations, functions in the context of multiset theory.

Many mathematicians have tried to study the properties of algebraic structures on multisets. As a result, the concept of Multiset group has been expanded to us. The name of the mathematicians who are notable in this field are A.M. Ibrahim & P.A. Ejegwa, S.K. Najmul *et al.*, Y. Tella & S. Daniel, P.A. Ejegwa. They completed researches about multiset group and explained it easily to us and also studied different types of results and properties.

S. Debnath & A. Debnath illustrated and defined *Mrings* and worked on some of their important theorems. Suma P and Sunil Jacob John also given a lot of contribution about *Mset* relations, *Mset* ring, *Mset* ideal and also created many results in these concepts.

Prelims:

Definition 1.1 [19]: A multiset or an $MsetY$ is a collection of some or all elements taken from a crisp set T with their frequency, that is elements with their number of repetitions. This frequency of a member $t \in T$ is denoted by $F_Y(t)$. We use $[T]^p$ as $Msetspace$, which is the collection of all such $Msets$ whose elements are taken from T with maximum number of frequency p .

Example 1.1: Suppose $T = \{a, b, c\}$ and $Y = \langle 2, a \rangle, \langle 4, c \rangle$.

here 'a' appeared 2 times, 'c' appeared 4 times, 'b' appeared 0 times.

So, $F_Y(a) = 2, F_Y(c) = 4, F_Y(b) = 0, F_Y(t)$ never be negative numbers.

Definition 1.2 [19]: Suppose $Y, Z \in [T]^p$ then Y is called a sub $Mset$ of Z , denoted by $Y \subseteq Z$ if, $F_Z(t) \geq F_Y(t) \forall t \in T$.

If there exist at least one $t \in T$ with above condition such that, $F_Y(t) < F_Z(t)$, then we say that Y is a proper sub $Mset$ of Z which is denoted by $Y \subset Z$.

Definition 1.3 [19]: Suppose $Y, Z \in [T]^p$, then $Y \cup Z$ and $Y \cap Z$ are defined as, $F_{Y \cup Z}(t) = \text{MAX}\{F_Y(t), F_Z(t)\}$ and $F_{Y \cap Z}(t) = \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Z(t)\}$, for all $t \in T$.

Definition 1.4 [20]: Suppose Y is an $Mset$ taken from a group $(T, *)$ and satisfies the following two conditions:

a. $F_Y(t * r) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r)\}$; for all $t, r \in T$.

b. $F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y(t)$ for any $t \in T$.

Then we say that Y is an $Mgroup$ taken from $(T, *)$.

We will use $MS[T]$ and $MG[T]$ to represent collection of sets of all $Msets$ and $Mgroups$ taken from a group $(T, *)$ respectively.

Example 1.2: Let $T = \{1, \omega, \omega^2\}$ and $Y = \langle 5, 1 \rangle, \langle 4, \omega^2 \rangle, \langle 4, \omega \rangle$, where ω is an imaginary cube root of unity, T will form a group with respect to the usual multiplication. Also, we can verify that Y will form an $Mgroup$ by following table.

.	1 (5)	u (4)	u ² (4)
1 (5)	1 (5)	u (4)	u ² (4)
u (4)	u (4)	u ² (4)	1 (5)
u ² (4)	u ² (4)	1 (5)	u (4)

Theorem 1.1 [22]: Suppose $Y \in MG[T]$, where $(T, *)$ is a group with identity element e then, (a) $F_Y(e) \geq F_Y(t)$ (b) $F_Y(t^p) \geq F_Y(t)$ for any $t \in T$

Proof: (a) $F_Y(e) = F_Y(t * t^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(t^{-1})\} = \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(t)\}$
 $= F_Y(t)$

(b) we can use mathematical induction to prove this.

Definition 1.5 [22]: Let $Y \in MS[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then,

$$Y^{-1} \in MS[T] \text{ and } F_{Y^{-1}}(t) = F_Y(t^{-1}).$$

Definition 1.6 [22]: Suppose $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group. Then $Z \in MS[T]$ is said to be a sub Mgroup of Y , if $Z \subseteq Y$ and $Z \in MG[T]$.

Theorem 1.2 [22]: $Y \in MG[T] \Leftrightarrow F_Y(t * r^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r)\}$,

$\forall t, r \in T$. where $(T, *)$ is a group.

Proof: Suppose, $Y \in MG[T]$

$$\text{Then, } F_Y(t * r^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r^{-1})\} = \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r)\} \forall t, r \in T.$$

For converse case,

$$F_Y(t * r^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r)\} \text{ holds } \forall t, r \in T.$$

$$\text{Now, } F_Y(e) = F_Y(t * t^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(t)\} = F_Y(t) \text{ for all } t \in T$$

Therefore, $F_Y(e) \geq F_Y(t)$ for all $t \in T$

$$\text{Now } F_Y(t) = F_Y(e * t) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(e), F_Y(t^{-1})\}$$

$$= F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y(e * t^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(e), F_Y(t)\} = F_Y(t) \forall t \in T.$$

So, $F_Y(t) = F_Y(t^{-1})$.

$$F_Y(t * r) = F_Y(t * (r^{-1})^{-1}) \geq \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r^{-1})\} = \text{MIN}\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r)\} \forall t, r \in T.$$

Hence Y is an M group.

Definition 1.7 [20]: $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group, is called an abelian M group over T if for any $t, r \in T$, $F_Y(t*r) = F_Y(r*t)$.

$AMG[T]$ is the Set of all possible abelian M groups over T .

Definition 1.8 [20]: $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group, is called a normal M group if $F_Y(t*r*t^{-1}) \geq F_Y(r)$ for any $t, r \in T$.

Definition 1.9 [54]: $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then Madhya of Y is denoted by $\mathcal{M}(Y)$ is an M set which is defined as,

$F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t) = 0$, where $F_Y(t*r) \neq F_Y(r*t)$ for some $r \in T$.

$F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t) = F_Y(t)$, where $F_Y(t*r) = F_Y(r*t) \forall r \in T$.

Note -It is very easy to show that if $Y \in MG[T]$ then, $\square(Y) \subseteq Y$.

Theorem 1.3 [54]: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then,

$e \in \mathcal{C}^r \square(Y)$ where r is the positive frequency.

Proof: It is very easy to prove.

Theorem 1.4 [54]: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then,

If $t \in \square(Y)$ with frequency greater than zero

$\Rightarrow t^{-1} \in \square(Y)$ with frequency greater than zero.

Proof: As $t \in \square(Y)$, $F_Y(t*r^{-1}) = F_Y(r^{-1}*t)$ for any r^{-1} of Y

$\Rightarrow F_Y((t*r^{-1})^{-1}) = F_Y((r^{-1}*t)^{-1}) \Rightarrow F_Y(r*t^{-1}) = F_Y(t^{-1}*r)$

So, $t^{-1} \in \square(Y)$ and $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t^{-1}) = F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y(t) = F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t) > 0$ [Hence proved]

Theorem 1.5 [54]: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group and if $t, r \in \square(Y)$ with positive frequency then, $t*r \in \square(Y)$ with positive frequency.

Proof: We can prove it very easily.

Theorem 1.6 [54]: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then

$\square(Y)$ is a sub M group of Y .

Proof: $\square(Y)$ is a sub M set of Y . So, we will only check, it will satisfy necessary & sufficient condition of M group or not.

Suppose, $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t) = 0$ or $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r) = 0$ for some $t, r \in T$

Then clearly, $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t*r^{-1}) \geq \min\{F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t), F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r)\}$.

Now if, $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t) \neq 0$ & $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r) \neq 0$ for some $t, r \in T$

$$F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t) = F_Y(t) > 0 \text{ \& } F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r) = F_Y(r) > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t^{-1}) > 0 \text{ \& } F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r^{-1}) > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t*r^{-1}) > 0. \text{ [By previous theorem]}$$

$$F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t*r^{-1}) \geq \min\{F_Y(t), F_Y(r)\}$$

$$= \min\{F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t), F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r)\}$$

Hence $F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t*r^{-1}) \geq \min\{F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(t), F_{\mathcal{M}(Y)}(r)\}$ for all $t, r \in T$.

Therefore, $\square(Y)$ is a sub M group of Y .

Definition 1.9.1[54]: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then $\text{Madhya } \mathcal{M}_Y(t)$ of an element $t \in T$ in Y is an M set defined as,

$$F_{\mathcal{M}_Y(t)}(r) = 0, \text{ where } r \in T \text{ and } F_Y(t*r) \neq F_Y(r*t).$$

$$F_{\mathcal{M}_Y(t)}(r) = F_Y(r), \text{ where } r \in T \text{ and } F_Y(t*r) = F_Y(r*t).$$

Theorem 1.7 [54]: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then $\square(Y)$ always belongs to $\square(Y)$ with positive frequency.

Proof: It is very easy to prove.

Main definitions with properties:

Definition 2.1: Frequency conjugate element: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group, then an element $r \in T$ is said to be F conjugate or frequency conjugate to $t \in T$, if there exist an element g in T such that, $F_Y(r) = F_Y(g*t*g^{-1})$.

Definition 2.2: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then for $t \in T$, $\text{Cl}_Y(t)$ is an M set such that, $F_{\text{Cl}_Y(t)}(r) = F_Y(r)$ if r is conjugate to t otherwise $F_{\text{Cl}_Y(t)}(r) = 0$.

Theorem 2.1: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group. If t is F conjugate to r then t^{-1} is also F conjugate to r^{-1} .

Proof: Since t is F conjugate to r ,

Therefore, $F_Y(t) = F_Y(g*r*g^{-1})$ for some g in T .

So, $F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y((g*r*g^{-1})^{-1}) \Rightarrow F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y((g^{-1})^{-1}*r^{-1}*g^{-1})$

$\Rightarrow F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y(g*r^{-1}*g^{-1})$.

Hence, t^{-1} is F conjugate to r^{-1} .

Theorem 2.2: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group.

If t is F conjugate to r then t^{-1} is also F conjugate to r .

Proof: Since t is F conjugate to r , $F_Y(t) = F_Y(g*r*g^{-1})$ for some g in T .

$\Rightarrow F_Y(t^{-1}) = F_Y(g*r*g^{-1})$. Hence, t^{-1} is F conjugate to r .

Theorem 2.3: Let $(T, *)$ is a group, $Y \in MG[T]$, and $F_Y(u)$ is positive for an element $u \in T$, then $u \in Cl_Y(u)$ with positive frequency.

Proof: Clearly element u is F conjugate to u here because,

$F_Y(u) = F_Y(e*u*e^{-1})$, where e is the identity element of T .

So, $F_{Cl_Y(u)}(u) = F_Y(u)$, which is positive.

Theorem 2.4: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group then $Cl_Y(u)$ is a Sub Mset of Y .

Proof: If $t \in Cl_Y(u)$ with positive frequency. Then, $F_{Cl_Y(u)}(t) = F_Y(t)$.

Now if $t \in Cl_Y(u)$ with zero frequency then two cases arise,

Case-1: If t is not F conjugate to u but $F_Y(t)$ positive.

Then obviously, $F_{Cl_Y(u)}(t) \leq F_Y(t)$.

Case-2: If t is not F conjugate to u and $F_Y(t) = 0$.

Then, $F_{Cl_Y(u)}(t) = F_Y(t)$.

Therefore, for all $t \in T$, $F_{Cl_Y(u)}(t) \leq F_Y(t)$. [Hence proved.]

Theorem 2.5: Let $Y \in MG[T]$ where $(T, *)$ is a group. If t, r are two elements of $\square(Y)$ with positive and same frequency then t is F conjugate to r .

Proof: Here, $f_Y(r) = f_Y(t) \Rightarrow f_Y(r * t^{-1} * t) = f_Y(t) \Rightarrow f_Y((r * t^{-1}) * t) = f_Y(t)$.

$\Rightarrow f_Y(t * (r * t^{-1})) = f_Y(t)$ [since t is the element of $\square(Y)$]

$\Rightarrow f_Y(t * r * t^{-1}) = f_Y(t)$. [Hence proved]

Future possible works: Considering the importance of this topic we can study and create some other results on frequency conjugate elements in future. We can prove some results in future like, if t and s are F conjugate to r then $t * s$ is also F conjugate to r or not, Frequency of $t * s$ in $Cl(u)$, $Cl(u)$ forms an M group or not, $Cl(u)$ forms a normal sub M group of Y or not etc.

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